

Improving the Urban Accessibility of Older Pedestrians using Multi-objective Optimization

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Abstract— Many countries around the world have witnessed the progressive ageing of their population, giving rise to a global concern to respond to the needs that this process will create. Besides the changes in the productive schemes and the evolution of the healthcare resources to new models, the accessibility of pedestrians belonging to this age range is grasping an increasing interest in urban planning processes. This work presents preliminary results of a framework that combines graph modeling and meta-heuristic optimization to inform decision makers in urban planning when deciding how to regenerate urban spaces taking into account pedestrian accessibility for the older people in urban areas with difficult orography. The goal of the framework is to decide where to deploy urban elements (mechanical ramps, escalators and lifts), so that an indirect measure of accessibility is improved while also accounting for the economical investment of the installation. We exploit the versatility of multi-objective evolutionary algorithms to tackle the underlying optimization problem. Experimental results of a case study located in the city of Santander (Spain) show that the proposed framework can support urban planners when making decisions regarding the accessibility of the public space.

Index Terms—Urban planning, pedestrian accessibility, combinatorial optimization, multi-objective evolutionary algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the beginning of the industrial revolution, the fraction of the population that lives in urban areas has grown steadily until today. Moreover, in the last 50 years this growth has risen sharply due to the rural-to-urban migration, specially in the Asian and African continents [1], [2]. In the words of the United Nations, in 2019 55% of world population lived in cities, while for 2050 this ratio is expected to reach 70%. Besides this massive trend, another concerning factor is population ageing, which is a direct consequence of a significant rise in life expectancy and low natality [3]. This phenomenon will result in the number of older people doubling in the next three decades, exceeding 1.500 million people in 2050. This represents a rise of 6.7%, reaching 16% of the world population aged 65 years or over [4]. These two factors do not only reshape the mean age of the city dwellers, but also their way of living, with a clear tendency to single-person households [4].

In practice, these factors pose a great challenge for city planners. The term *age-friendly-cities* refers to those cities aiming to be more adapted to the needs of the older people, specifically by supporting “active ageing by optimizing

opportunities for health, participation and security to enhance the quality of life as people age” [5], [6]. In an attempt to measure the age-friendliness level of a city, the World Health Organization (WHO) has defined 88 core age-friendly features [5], among which universal accessibility is arguably one of the most significant characteristics. This concept can be defined as the opportunity to access/reach community resources, services and recreational facilities [7]. Thus, improving the universal accessibility for older people leads to a better quality of life and contributes to the prosperity of society as a whole.

To realize this vision, new disruptive technologies such as Artificial Intelligence, Big Data and digital twins are enabling new methods for optimizing and improving urban accessibility. Although there are some scarce examples of their use (e.g., [8]–[12]), the exploitation of these technologies for the aforementioned purpose is still in an embryonic stage. Therefore, great potential remains untapped in the use of new technologies to support Decision Support Systems (DSS) and related processes in public policies [13], [14], including urban planning. In recent decades, both private companies and public entities are already using DSS frameworks endowed with avant-garde technological functionalities. Nevertheless, there is still a long way to go towards improving further DSS.

In this work, we contribute to this research niche by designing a novel framework based on multi-objective evolutionary optimization that supports decision making when it comes to the improvement of urban accessibility for older people in urban areas with sloping streets. To this end, the focus is placed on enhancing decisions related to the installation of accessibility infrastructure in existing urban environments. In this context, traditional decision making still prevails over newer/modern methodologies, which lag significantly behind in practice [15]. Actions to be carried out with urban elements are mainly decided based on heuristics, statistical studies, audits or the expert knowledge of experienced urban planners [16]–[18], and are usually planned in 2 dimensions. These processes are often slow, manual, prone to error and, in some cases, uninformed with evidence.

This work intends to showcase the utility of tools from the Computational Intelligence realm for strategic (i.e., mid-to long-term) decision making processes related to urban accessibility. Among them, simulation-based optimization has been often used to model, characterize and optimize urban pedestrian mobility. Simulation engines have today achieved

unprecedented levels of precision and fidelity, but demand an overly high computational cost for supporting strategic decisions. By contrast, the framework described in this work resorts to a graph model of the problem, which leads to less accurate results but lower computational effort and higher flexibility and scalability than simulation-based alternatives. Once the different factors affecting urban accessibility are embedded in a geo-referenced graph, we tackle a specific multi-objective problem with evolutionary algorithms to exemplify the potential of the framework: the cost-efficient installation of ramps, escalators and lifts that allow older pedestrians to traverse sloping streets in their way towards points of interest (e.g., day-care facilities, drugstores or supermarkets). Results from a use case located in Santander (Spain) will be discussed to display the usage of the framework in real-world settings.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section II expands preliminary concepts and related work in the existing literature. Section III provides a detailed description of the proposed framework. The experimental setup and datasets used for the case study are detailed in Section IV. Section V presents and discusses the results obtained from our experiments and, finally, Section VI concludes by pointing out future research lines departing from our findings.

II. BACKGROUND

As mentioned in the introduction, this work steps on two main research areas: accessibility of urban environments (the *goal*) and optimization techniques (the *method*). In this section we briefly overview contributions reported in the past that relate to these areas, highlighting the novelty of the proposed framework with respect to the state of the art.

A. Urban Accessibility: Concept and Recent History

First of all, it is worth reviewing the concept of accessibility, which is not unique and whose interpretations have evolved significantly throughout time. One of the first definitions was that of Hansen in 1956 [19]. Hansen defined accessibility as the “potential of opportunities for interaction”, prescribing formulae for its quantification. Later, in 1980 Koenig in [20] defined several accessibility indicators that gave greater precision to urban and transport models. In 1996, the European Concept for Accessibility (ECA) was established in response to a request from the European Commission. Among other endeavors, ECA was commanded to rethink the definition of accessibility and derive new criteria to evaluate it effectively [21]. As a result, in the report published in [21], ECA defined universal accessibility as “a basic feature of the built environment. It is the condition that makes it possible to arrive, leave and use houses, shops, and public places. It enables people to participate in the social and economic activities for which the built environment is designed” [21]. In 2003, ECA published its second review [22], where the concept of universal accessibility was further refined by adding social reasons to build an environment accessible for all.

In recent years the way in which urban accessibility is measured towards its improvement has undergone a remark-

able transformation. Modern Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) such as the Internet of Things (IoT) have progressively permeated into the design, management and optimization of the so-called Smart City paradigm [23], [24]. While in the past simple techniques were used to measure urban accessibility such as audits [25] or surveys [17], [18], today widely used technologies such as GPS [26] or GIS tools [9], [27], [28] are utilized instead for the same purpose. Moreover, Artificial Intelligence is also coming into play as an enabler for informed decision making in urban regeneration. Data-based machine learning models [10], [29] – including deep convolutional neuronal networks [30] – have been used to reduce the resources and time needed for analyzing deficiencies and possible improvements of urban environments.

When the focus is placed on enhancing urban accessibility, several studies have resorted to AI-based solvers for addressing different optimization problems related to this objective. We now proceed by reviewing these previous works to underscore the contribution of the proposed framework.

B. Optimization for Urban Accessibility

A few examples of the use of simulation-based optimization applied to the urban environment can be found in the literature from the perspective of universal or pedestrian accessibility. Traditionally the hybridization of meta-heuristic optimization algorithms with simulation engines has enjoyed a more profitable development in problems related to vehicular traffic, e.g., [31]–[34]. Significantly lower research efforts have been invested in the use of simulation-based optimization for urban accessibility. This hybrid approach can yield reliable microscopic-scale results in physically restricted environments (as for the modeling of crowd dynamics in buildings). On the contrary, the huge human and computational efforts needed to realistically simulate urban environments at macroscopic scales make simulation-based optimization not a suitable approach for problems related to urban accessibility.

Despite these caveats, some few contributions have embraced simulation-based optimization by restricting their scope to those components of the urban ecosystem that can be modeled effectively via simulation. One of these components is public transportation: for instance, the work by Calabró et al. [35] uses simulation-based Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) to improve the public transport routing service in Catania (Italy). By reducing the number of areas with little coverage for buses, their approach increases the universal accessibility of the neighborhoods involved in the area under study.

A relaxed yet more flexible way of representing the multiple factors that impact urban accessibility is the usage of graphs with geo-referenced information. A graph model of the urban environment combined with meta-heuristic solvers can overcome the inherent limitations of simulation-based optimization, namely, the complexity of reliably modeling micro-scale dynamics at street level in a city. Graphs are valid as an informational framework for the city since space-time factors of relevance for urban accessibility (including the third dimension) and the quality of transit in the city (pollution,

lighting, etc.) can be easily geo-referenced and mapped onto this data structure. Several examples can be found using graphs for the optimization of accessibility for people with reduced mobility, such as wheelchair users or the older people. Bolten et al. [36] have used graph theory to parametrize the streets from the point of view of wheelchair accessibility. Rahaman et al. [37] have broadened the scope of [36] by devising a Contour-based Accessible Path Routing Algorithm (CAPRA) based on the well-known A* heuristic. CAPRA yields several alternative routes that enhance the accessibility of older people. Following the same rationale, Sasaki et al. [38] study how to find routes for a walk taking into account quantitative measures of their safety, amenity and walkability. Specifically, they combine the A* path algorithm and a Genetic Algorithm (GA) to compute subpaths maximizing those factors.

All in all, most research activity carried out to date at the crossroads between optimization and urban accessibility has been focused on finding alternative routes that are more accessible for mobility-constrained users (e.g., older people, wheelchair users), rather than on enhancing the accessibility of existing trajectories. In practice, older people are not used to changing their mobility habits. Major changes in routes can cause disorientation in people of advanced age, leading to a security risk for these citizens. Moreover, in some scenarios there might be no alternative routes that could comply with the accessibility requirements of the target population, making the discovery of accessible routes an unreachable goal, and discouraging older pedestrians from having an active life.

Despite its inherent practical value, to the best of our knowledge there is no prior work in the literature seeking to improve the accessibility of existing routes by making active interventions in the urban elements that affect this objective. This is the rationale for the framework described in what follows, which combines a graph-based model and multi-objective optimization to improve urban accessibility through the deployment of urban infrastructures, such as mechanical ramps, escalators and lifts.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

As anticipated in the previous section, the solutions proposed so far for the improvement of urban accessibility involve the creation of new walking routes, leaving aside the upgrade or modification of the existing ones. Thus, we propose a novel method based on the combination of graph-based models of the urban environment and meta-heuristic algorithms for multi-objective optimization.

Figure 1 depicts a schematic diagram of the proposed framework, which departs from the construction of a geo-referenced multi-edge graph $\mathcal{G} \doteq \{\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E}, [f_1, \dots, f_M]\}$, where \mathcal{V} represents the set of $|\mathcal{V}| = V$ nodes or vertices of the graph (street junctions of the urban area under consideration); \mathcal{E} is the set of edges connecting every pair of vertices (street segments), and $f_m : \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^+$ is a function assigning a non-negative weight to each edge. Each of such functions $[f_m(\cdot)]_{m=1}^M$ accounts for an aspect of the urban environment that affect the accessibility of older people, such as the time

taken to walk and traverse the edge at hand, the average daily thermal comfort of the street segment, the proximity to public transportation, or the width of pavements, to cite a few. We do not assume any symmetry in the weights of edges connecting every pair of nodes, namely, $f_m(v, v')$ is not necessarily equal to $f_m(v', v)$ for $m \in [1, \dots, M]$ and $v \neq v'$. Geo-referencing extends the definition of graph \mathcal{G} with the coordinates $(x(v), y(v))$ and elevation $h(v) \forall v \in \mathcal{V}$.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the proposed framework.

Before proceeding further, it is important to pause at the modeling possibilities brought by the construction of the aforementioned graph. We recall that edges \mathcal{E} represent streets or walkable paths of the urban area under study, while nodes \mathcal{V} correspond to junctions where two or more streets collide. The annotation of the geographical coordinates of nodes over the urban area under study can be provided by topographical GIS databases, whereas other variables affecting the mobility and accessibility of older pedestrians can be fed from Open Data portals, which are often made available by city councils of medium-to-large size. Furthermore, the assumption of several, differently weighted edges between every pair of nodes permits to measure different objectives related to accessibility.

An intuitive example of the multi-criteria decision making support eased by the framework is the time taken by an older person to traverse a certain street segment (v, v') , which can be thought to be highly dependent on 1) its slope $\theta(v, v')$:

$$\theta(v, v') = \arctan \left(\frac{h(v') - h(v)}{\sqrt{(x(v) - x(v'))^2 + (y(v) - y(v'))^2}} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\theta(v, v') \in \mathbb{R}[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$; and 2) the length of the segment, given by:

$$\ell(v, v') = \sqrt{(x(v) - x(v'))^2 + (y(v) - y(v'))^2 + (h(v) - h(v'))^2}.$$

Based on these definitions, a widely model to compute the walking speed as a function of the slope is the so-called Tobler's hiking function [39], which establishes:

$$S(v, v') = 6 \exp(-3.5 \cdot |\tan \theta(v, v') + 0.05|) \text{ [km/h]}, \quad (2)$$

from where the walking time of the edge (v, v') yields as:

$$T(v, v') = \ell(v, v') / S(v, v') \text{ [h]}. \quad (3)$$

where we assume that $\ell(v, v')$ is measured in kilometers. Since our framework aims at the accessibility of older people, the above general model must be modified to take into account their inability to traverse a street segment featuring a slope higher than a maximum θ_{max} . Therefore, the speed provided by this modified hiking function $S_\diamond(v, v')$ is defined as:

$$S_\diamond(v, v') = S(v, v') \cdot \begin{cases} \beta_\diamond & \theta(v, v') \leq \theta_{max}, \\ 0.01 \cdot \beta_\diamond & \theta(v, v') > \theta_{max}, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where $S(v, v')$ is given in Expression (2), and $\beta_\diamond \in \mathbb{R}(0, 1]$ is a multiplicative factor that induces a penalty due to the age of the pedestrian w.r.t. the nominal maximum speed of $S(v, v')$ (i.e., 6 km/h at $\theta(v, v') = 2.86^\circ$). Therefore, the total time taken to go from an origin node v_o to a destination node v_d through graph \mathcal{G} is given by:

$$T(v_o, v_d) = \sum_{(v, v') \in \mathcal{E}_{o,d}} \ell(v, v') / S_\diamond(v, v'), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{E}_{o,d} \subseteq \mathcal{E}$ is the ordered group of nodes that compose the minimum-cost path from v_o to v_d .

An optimization problem formulated based on the above definitions is to discover which interventions – understood as the installation of urban elements aimed to improve physical accessibility, including ramps, escalators and lifts – should be done for the average path time between a selected subset \mathcal{V}_o of origin nodes and a subset of destinations \mathcal{V}_d to be minimized. The decision involves not only how many interventions should be done (K), but also which elements to deploy, their characteristics (e.g. length of a ramp), and in which edge over the urban area at hand. Each intervention can be denoted as a triplet (e_k, t_k, \mathbf{c}_k) , where $e_k \in \mathcal{E}$ indicates the edge where the intervention is done; $t_k \in \{R, E, L\}$ (Ramp, Escalator, Lift) establishes its type; and \mathbf{c}_k is a type-dependent vector of features/functionality of the installed asset.

We model the impact of the installation of any of these urban assets on a given edge of the graph by modifying again the Tobler's hiking function as:

$$S_\diamond^{acc}(v, v') = \begin{cases} S_\diamond(v, v') \text{ (Expr. (4)) if } e_k \neq (v, v'), \text{ else:} \\ S_R \text{ if } t_k = R, \theta(v, v') \in (\theta_{max}, \theta_{max}^R] \\ S_E \text{ if } t_k = E, \theta(v, v') \in (\theta_{max}^R, \theta_{max}^E] \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $\theta_{max} < \theta_{max}^R < \theta_{max}^E < 90^\circ$ denote the maximum slopes at which ramps and escalators can be installed; and S_R (S_E) stands for the nominal speed at which a ramp (escalator) operate. The average path time can be then computed as:

$$T_{avg}(\mathcal{V}_o, \mathcal{V}_d) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{V}_o| |\mathcal{V}_d|} \sum_{v_o \in \mathcal{V}_o} \sum_{v_d \in \mathcal{V}_d} \sum_{(v, v') \in \mathcal{E}_{o,d}} T^{acc}(v, v'), \quad (7)$$

where:

$$T^{acc}(v, v') = \begin{cases} \frac{\ell(v, v')}{S_\diamond(v, v')} \text{ if } \nexists e_k = (v, v'), \text{ else:} \\ \frac{\gamma_k \ell(v, v')}{S_\diamond^{acc}(v, v')} + \frac{(1-\gamma_k) \ell(v, v')}{S_\diamond(v, v')} \text{ if } t_k \in \{R, E\}, \\ \frac{S_L}{\Delta_h(v, v')} + \frac{S_\diamond(v, v')}{\Delta_{xy}(v, v')} \text{ if } t_k = L, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta_h(v, v') = |h(v) - h(v')|$ (elevation difference); $\Delta_{xy}(v, v') = \sqrt{(x(v) - x(v'))^2 + (y(v) - y(v'))^2}$ (horizontal distance); and $\gamma_k \in \mathbb{R}(0, 1]$ denotes the relative length of the installed asset with respect to the total length of the edge. Without loss of generality we assume that the vector of features \mathbf{c}_k of the installed element reduces to its relative length.

A second objective that can be formulated for our devised framework is the total cost of the installation of the urban elements for accessibility. A straightforward albeit illustrative simplification is to assume that the cost $C(e_k, t_k, \gamma_k)$ incurred by the installation of the asset comprises:

$$C(e_k, t_k, \gamma_k) = C_{fix}(t_k) + C_{var}(t_k, e_k, \gamma_k), \quad (9)$$

namely, a fixed term $C_{fix}(t_k)$, which only depends on its type (e.g., engine, workforce, supporting materials); and a variable term $C_{var}(t_k, e_k, \gamma_k)$ assumed to increase linearly with the effective length of the installation (namely, $\gamma_k \cdot \ell(v, v')$ if $(v, v') = e_k$). Minimizing the total costs of the urban intervention can be tackled jointly with the minimization of the average path time given in Expression (7), yielding a problem with two objectives formulated as:

$$\min_{K, \{(e_k, t_k, \gamma_k)\}_{k=1}^K} \left[T_{avg}(\mathcal{V}_o, \mathcal{V}_d), \sum_{k=1}^K C(e_k, t_k, \gamma_k) \right], \quad (10)$$

subject to: $\gamma_k \ell(v, v') < \ell_{max}, \forall k : t_k \neq \text{lift}, (v, v') = e_k,$

for which the goal is to find solutions close to the Pareto trade-off between the accessibility improvement enabled by the installed elements (given by the first objective) and the investment required to implement them in practice (second objective). Such objectives are conflicting with each other: the deployment of ramps, escalators or lifts will reduce the walking time and potentially enable new paths that otherwise could not be traversed by older pedestrians. However, the more infrastructure is to be deployed, the higher the costs will be. The goal of the optimization problem is, hence, to find diverse options for the deployment (as per K and $\{(e_k, t_k, \gamma_k)\}_{k=1}^K$) that differently – yet near optimally in the sense of Pareto – balance their objectives. A further technical constraint is set to limit the length of the ramps and escalators below ℓ_{max} meters.

To deal with the aforementioned problem we will benefit from the renowned potential of multi-objective evolutionary algorithms to deal with optimization problems comprising multiple objectives defined over mixed continuous ($\{\lambda_k\}_{k=1}^K$) and discrete ($K, \{t_k, e_k\}_{k=1}^K$) search spaces. The solution encoding (genotype) is designed in close resemblance with the phenotype imposed by the problem:

$$[(e_1, t_1, \gamma_1), (e_2, t_2, \gamma_2) \dots, (e_{K_{max}}, t_{K_{max}}, \gamma_{K_{max}})], \quad (11)$$

namely, a structure divided in K_{max} triplets, where we insert an additional type in the alphabet of t_k (i.e., $t_k \in \{R, E, L, \emptyset\}$) to allow for deployments involving the installation of $K < K_{max}$ elements. Departing from one solution encoded as above, the times needed to traverse each of the

edges of the graph are updated accordingly, and the shortest path between every pair of origin and destination nodes in \mathcal{V}_o and \mathcal{V}_d is computed via the Dijkstra algorithm [40]. Computing the average path time and the cost associated with the solution at hand permits to characterize its dominance in the space of objectives, whereas the specific multi-objective evolutionary approach in use establishes the search operators applied to perform the search for Pareto-optimal solutions efficiently.

A. Further Use Cases of the Framework

Before proceeding with the presentation and discussion of the use case, it is worth mentioning other objectives and sources of urban information that could be added to the framework, spanning further optimization criteria and applications related to the improvement of urban accessibility. New edge weights could be added between every pair of nodes in \mathcal{G} to indicate, for instance, the proximity to bus or taxi stops, parking spaces for people with reduced mobility, green zones or locations of cultural interest (e.g. museums). Unless pollution and/or acoustic sensors were available on site, information about the intensity of road traffic could be used as an indirect measure of the intensity of noise or the level of pollution. Similarly, the exact location of waste containers, the presence of bike lanes or irrigation sensors might be also factors affecting the path of an older citizen, which can be also georeferenced, mapped as additional weights over the graph, and considered as new objectives and/or constraints.

IV. USE CASE: SANTANDER (SPAIN)

In order to showcase the use of the proposed framework in a real-world setting, we design a use case located in the *Entrehuertas* neighborhood of Santander (North of Spain). Streets of this part of the city are characterized by large slopes, laying a suitable scenario for the cost-efficient deployment of urban accessibility infrastructure. We establish the latitude and longitude bounds of the area under study to $[43.46855^\circ, 43.46424^\circ]$ and $[-3.79667^\circ, -3.80997^\circ]$, respectively.

Fig. 2. Location of the use case discussed in the experiments of our work, together with a 3D representation of its urban topography (using LiDAR data) and the graph extracted via OSMnx/Open Street Maps.

Elevation data were retrieved from the National Geographic Institute (IGN) of the Spanish Government [41]. Specifically, a

Digital Terrain Model (DTM) of resolution equal to five meters was collected, creating a highly accurate 3D model of the terrain. On the other hand, the graph of the area is captured by the *OSMnx* Python library [42], which interfaces to the well-known Open Street Maps mapping service [43]. To increase further the spatial resolution of the graph, we augmented the number of nodes by adding 5 equally spaced nodes on every edge (v, v') . Elevation data for every node was mapped from the aforementioned DTM models based on the proximity of its $(x(v), y(v))$ coordinates to the points of the DTM grid.

Fig. 3. (a) Graph with annotated elevation data for every node (extrapolated nodes not depicted for the sake of visual clarity); (b) Histogram of street slopes of the graph.

Once the graph has been constructed, we select $|\mathcal{V}_o| = 11$ origin nodes and $|\mathcal{V}_d| = 3$ destination nodes for the routes over which the average path time will be computed as per (7). Destination nodes are carefully chosen to be close to points of interest for older citizens, whereas origins are scattered uniformly at random over the nodes of the scenario under study. If available, municipal citizen databases could be analyzed to tailor the selection of origin nodes, e.g., by selecting those located in areas with a high density of aged inhabitants. The chosen origin (●) and destination (●) nodes are highlighted in Figure 3.a.

TABLE I
PARAMETERS AND VALUES SET FOR THE USE CASE

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
ℓ_{max}	100 m	θ_{max}^R	12°
S_R	0.4 m/s	θ_{max}^S	20°
S_E	0.5 m/s	β_\circ	Max. speed equal to 1.1 m/s at slope -2°
S_L	1 m/s	$C_{fix}(t_k)$	25k€ (ramp), 40k€ (escalator), 100k€ (lift)
θ_{max}	8°	$C_{var}(t_k)$	6.8k€/m (ramp), 7.5k€/m (escalator), 10k€/m (lift)

Table I summarizes the values set for the parameters driving the walking speed model, together with those from which the costs of every installed asset can be computed. Regarding the search algorithm under consideration, we resort to the renowned Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II [44]) meta-heuristic solver for multi-objective optimization, which is arguably among the most widely utilized solvers for

Fig. 4. (a) Approximation of the Pareto front between average path time and cost of the urban infrastructure deployed for accessibility improvement (color denotes the value of K); (b) to (f) three-dimensional graphs representing the shortest paths from each origin node to each destination node (black bold lines), together with the edges in which assets are deployed (in red). Each caption denotes the objective values and the number of installed urban elements.

multi-objective optimization problems to date. The integer part of the encoded solution (representing the type of asset t_k and edge e_k in which it is to be installed) is evolved separately from the real-valued part of the genotype (corr., the relative length γ_k). In both cases adapted version of the Simulated Binary Crossover (SBX) with probability 0.7 and distribution index equal to 20 are used. Integer random mutation and polynomial mutation are respectively applied to every part of the solution with an equal probability 0.1. The population size is equal to 30, and the search is stopped when reaching 10^4 evaluated solutions. A maximum number of $K_{max} = 20$ assets were considered. At this point it must be noted that the tailored selection of these hyper-parameter values and search operators fall beyond the scope of this work. Therefore, we restrict our discussion to the qualitative assessment of the Pareto front estimation produced by the specific algorithmic configuration in use. Nevertheless, the presented framework accommodates the usage of any other multi-objective solver characterized by other selection, crossover, mutation or replacement strategies.

Results discussed in what follows do not consider several independent runs. Although the use of the jMetalPy library [45] for the implementation of the framework could ease a performance comparison among different meta-heuristic solvers (what could require evaluating statistically the produced fronts over different runs), we concentrate the discussion on the

qualitative and quantitative assessment of the output of one single run of the framework. This comparison is delegated for future research, as is clarified later in the conclusions.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The approximated front resulting from the application of the proposed framework over the scenario defined in the previous section is depicted in Figure 4.a. In this plot different colors are used to highlight, in the front, those installations comprising the same number of $K \leq K_{max}$ effectively deployed infrastructure. As such, the rightmost point corresponds to the case when no assets are installed, reflecting that without any intervention the average path time from each origin node in \mathcal{V}_o to every destination in \mathcal{V}_d is slightly above 4,500 seconds (approximately 1 hour and 15 minutes), at zero cost (as expected). However, we observe that the framework progressively increases the number of urban infrastructure installations from $K = 1$ to $K = 5$, with a correspondingly increasing expenditure. It is interesting to notice that the front is composed of linear segments comprising points sharing the same value of K , in which the solutions only differ in terms of the value of $\ell(v, v')$, i.e. the length of the installation. This conforms to intuition, as the relationship between cost and length is set to be linear as per Expression (9), and so is the ratio between length and path time through the speed imposed

by the Tobler’s hiking function, in both its seminal definition and the modification done in this work. As a matter of fact, vertical gaps (cost differences) between segments coincide with the value of $C_{fix}(t_k)$ (fixed cost term) of the extra urban element added in the new segment. It is interesting to see that the framework discovers deployments of infrastructure for expenditures up to 400k€, reducing the average path time down to approximately 35 minutes.

To delve further into the solutions represented in the approximated Pareto front, we turn the focus of the discussion on Figures 4.b, 4.c, 4.d, 4.e and 4.f. These plots exemplify the actual interventions represented by different points of the estimated Pareto front, indicating in red which edges of the three-dimensional graph of Figure 3 are selected for the installation of urban infrastructure. We also highlight in these plots the minimum-time path connecting origin (●) to destination (●) nodes. A first visual inspection at these minimum-time paths reveals a high spatial correlation between them, in the sense that shortest paths with less number of nodes are contained within those comprising a higher number of nodes. Consequently, the proposed framework tends to install assets in edges belonging to such paths rather than exploring possibilities in isolated edges that only contribute to the accessibility improvement of a unique path. This is a consequence of the spatial correlation between shortest paths: an intervention in an edge of these paths yields an improvement in the shortest paths between several origin-destination node pairs, hence pushing down the average path time objective further than an isolated intervention that could affect just one single origin-destination pair.

Although the scenario discussed heretofore favors the existence of correlated minimum paths, this interpretation of the results must be done with caution and warned about the potential change in the shortest path caused by a newly added urban infrastructure. In other urban spaces with more sparsely located points of interest, such minimum paths could diverge, paving the way for local changes of the optimal path from every origin that could take their place in the estimated Pareto front. This, unfortunately, is largely dependent on the geographical profile and constraints existing in the location of interest. Nevertheless, we note that the application of the proposed framework can suggest which cost-efficient deployments can be done, no matter whether they entail a change of the shortest paths or, as exemplified by the discussed results, only improves the accessibility of their compounding edges.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The progressive ageing of the urban population has spurred the interest towards improving the accessibility of urban spaces by this collective. When it comes to addressing this objective via the installation of urban infrastructure, decision making has traditionally relied on expert knowledge, with scarce support of modern ICT technologies. The framework presented in this manuscript has showcased the utility of Artificial Intelligence – in particular, graph modeling and multiobjective optimization – to decide which accessibility

infrastructure to deploy and where to install over an urban area. The conflicting interplay between the improvement of the accessibility and the cost of the installation trace a Pareto front composed of solutions (deployments) that differently trade one objective for the other. Results from a real-world use case located in a neighborhood of the city of Santander (northern Spain) have been examined, concluding that the design of the optimal deployment of infrastructure for urban accessibility can be significantly informed by the output of the framework, accounting at the same time for installation constraints, the topography of the streets belonging to the urban environments, and smoothly allowing for the insertion of further criteria in the problem itself. Hence, this framework can be useful as a tool that supports urban planners and designers when making decisions regarding the accessibility of the public space.

Research efforts in the future are planned in a manifold of directions. Resounding the last statement above, we envision extending the functionalities and criteria of the developed framework by feeding the underlying graph with open data of relevance for the accessibility and enjoyability of the path, including pollution, environmental noise, thermal comfort, closeness to green areas and the like. From the algorithmic point of view, we will perform a benchmark of different multi-objective meta-heuristic solvers using checkpoints at several generation quotas and quantitative indicators of spread and dominance. A principled comparison among different multi-objective meta-heuristic solvers will be also pursued, comprising a fine-grained tuning of their search operators and hyper-parameter values. Finally, other geographical areas will be investigated, specially those where seasonalities along the year must be considered in several of the objectives (e.g. solar irradiation at floor level in southern areas of Europe).

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